

Effect of phosphorus fertilization on “priming” of native phosphorus by rice in acid soils of Assam

P. K. Bora, associate professor (soils), Assam Agricultural University, Jorhat 13; and N. N. Goswami, professor (soils), Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 12, India

Four typical rice-growing soils of Assam received three levels of phosphorus under continuous submergence and continuous moist conditions in the greenhouse. The uptake of soil phosphorus

was determined by radiochemical analysis. The quantity of “primed native phosphorus” was calculated:

$$\text{“Primed native phosphorus” (uptake in mg/pot)} = \frac{[(\text{Total-P uptake} - {}^{32}\text{P tagged fertilizer-P uptake}) - \text{Soil-P uptake (control plot)}]}{\text{uptake (control plot)}}$$

Fertilization with phosphorus as superphosphate increased the dry matter yield of rice and phosphorus (see table) uptake. The contribution of superphosphate not only was direct but was due to its “priming effect” on the uptake of native soil phosphorus — probably by

helping in the early vigorous growth of roots to exploit more soil. Under continuous submergence, the quantity of primed soil phosphorus of different levels of phosphorus fertilization was significant compared to the fertilizer phosphorus uptake by the crop at those levels. The results suggest that fertilizer phosphate application under continuous submergence is a beneficial practice that allows use of the immobilized soil phosphorus by the rice crop. ■

Quantity of “primed native soil phosphorus” at various rates of phosphate fertilization (SSP)^a under different moisture regimes during 1978. India.

Location	Uptake of “primed native soil phosphorus” (mg/pot) by the rice crop								
	Continuous submergence (M1)			Continuous moist (M2)			Av of M1 + M2		
	P1	P2	Mean of P1 + P2	P1	P2	Mean of P1+ P2	P1	P2	Mean of P1+ P2
Titabar	23.76	33.15	28.45	8.80	7.40	8.10	16.28	20.28	18.28
Dergaon	19.76	48.31	34.03	5.32	5.07	5.19	12.54	26.69	19.61
Golaghat	31.07	24.17	27.62	1.36	1.20	1.28	16.22	12.69	14.45
Tengakhat	31.06	33.58	32.32	10.60	7.65	9.13	20.83	20.61	20.72
Mean for all soils	26.41	34.80	30.61	6.52	5.33	5.93	16.47	20.07	—

^aSSP = single superphosphate. Phosphorus levels were P1 (60 kg P₂O₅/ha) and P2 (120 kg P₂O₅/ha). The rice was Pusa 2-21.

Rice-based cropping systems

Effect of rainfall pattern on the shift in farmers’ rice cropping patterns in Bangladesh

M. Zahidul Hoque, Nizam Uddin Ahmed, Afzal Hossain, and Mainur Rahman Siddiqui, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

A severe and prolonged drought in 1979 affected the cropping patterns and crop yields in many areas of Bangladesh. The rainfall pattern and the cropping patterns that farmers followed were monitored at a rainfed, double-rice crop (aus-T. aman) cropping systems research site at Bhogra, Joydebpur, Dacca, and compared with those of 1978.

The 1978 rainfall pattern was normal and unimodal (see figure). The fields received enough rainfall by April to

Rainfall pattern and farmers’ rice cropping patterns in 1978 and 1979 at a rainfed double-rice-crop area, Bhogra, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh. Areas of other cropping patterns are not shown in figure (1978 = 8%, 1979 = 14%). HYV = high yielding varieties.

enable the farmers to transplant the first rice (aus) crop. The farmers grew a double rice crop on 92% of the area. Sixty percent of the area was planted to a high yielding variety (HYV) aus rice — local t. aman rice followed by a pattern of HYV aus—HYV t. aman (16% of the area). In 1978, the ratio of land under HYV and local varieties was 10:8.4.

In 1979 an early season drought lasted until June. The total rainfall in 1978 and 1979 were 2,389 mm and 1,668 mm.

Precipitation was higher (182 mm) in the last 3 months of 1979 than in that period in 1978 (12 mm). Although the HYV aus—local t. aman pattern remained the main cropping pattern in 1979, its area decreased to 32%. The hectareage under the local aus—local t. aman pattern increased from 8% in 1978 to 28% in 1979. The HYV aus—HYV t. aman and local aus—HYV t. aman pattern used in 1978 completely disappeared in 1979, and a new cropping pattern emerged —a

single HYV or local rice crop. The delayed onset of the 1979 rains delayed the start of the first crop, which ultimately affected the entire cropping pattern, often making a second rice crop impossible. The ratio of HYV to local variety hectareage in 1979 was 5.5:9.1.

The experience left a challenge for cropping systems scientists: to develop suitable alternative cropping patterns for suboptimum weather conditions. ■

The International Rice Research Institute

P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines